

VARIMA(3,1,3) Model based RTT Estimation using RSSI

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Abstract – The Received Signal Strength (RSS) of wireless Lan (WLAN) varies due to environmental changes and technical factors such as obstacle in the signal path, path loss, link quality and climatical changes. Many of the protocols takes the RSS as a parameter to improve the performance of the data communication. In the cross-layer architecture, the network parameters from a layer are used by the non-adjacent layers which is considered as violation of standard in ISO-OSI reference model. TCP protocol from transport layer needs the RSS of the sender which is from the physical layer, to improve the performance of the congestion control mechanism. The RSS is one of the influencing parameters for estimating the Round-Trip Time (RTT) of a packet which is then used to calculate the size of the congestion window size of TCP. Whenever the link quality decreases, the corresponding RSS decreases and RTT increases. Therefore, it is necessary to relate RSS and RTT. This relation of RTT and RSS may be used to determine the congestion window size which improves the performance of TCP. In this paper, we use the time series analysis to model the RSS and RTT. In order to model the RSS and RTT, we collected RSS and RTT values from different location. Based on the exploratory data analysis, we found that Vector Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average (VARIMA) is suitable to model the RSS and RTT. The proposed model VARIMA(3,1,3) is closely suited for prediction of RSS and RTT.

Keywords: TCP, Congestion control, RTT, RSS, Time series analysis, VARIMA model

I. Introduction

The IEEE 802.11 WLAN standard is a network access technology for providing connectivity between wireless stations and wired networking infrastructures. In WLAN, the RSSI is a indication of the power level being received by the miniature antenna. The higher the RSSI, then stronger the signal. Due to multiple reflections from various object, the electromagnetic waves from the sender travel along different paths of varying lengths. The strengths of the waves decrease as the distance between the transmitter and receiver increases. It causes the changes in RTT estimation also. Many protocol such as TCP takes the RTT for estimation of retransmission timer and packet loss distinguishing. Therefore, the RSS and RTT are two metrics for estimating distance, link quality, and network performance. RSS experiences the signal attenuation over distance while the RTT is the delay experienced by signal traveling from the sender and back. Although, the RSS and RTT are two different metrics used for difference purposes, they are indirectly related through distance.

The RSS and RTT are dynamically varying because they vary over time due to mobility, environmental dynamics, interference, and network congestion. These temporal correlations between the RSS and RTT can be modelled using time series analysis. Hence, in this paper, we attempt to model the RSS-RTT using time series analysis. The proposed VARIMA model predicts the RTT accurately using RSS.

The rest of the paper is organized as follow. Section 2 describes the various RTT and RSS modeling using the time series analysis. Section 3 discusses the experimental setup and data collection. Section 4 presents exploratory data analysis of RSS and RTT and the proposed VARIMA model. We conclude the paper in the section 5.

II. Related Works

There are many models used to estimate the RSS in literature [1-7] because it is highly sensitive to environment factors such as multipath fading, shadowing, and interference. Similarly, there are many models used to estimate the RTT because it is also highly influenced by processing delay, queuing delay, communication overheads, and medium access contention. RSS and RTT models reflect the channel quality and network delay because both parameters relay distance. Therefore, a joint RSS-RTT models help to reduce the ambiguity in distance estimation.

[1] discusses the unique characteristics of RSSI signal changes to observe if there is a pattern between time domain and frequency domain and to study the variance of RSSI signal because of multipath fading, doppler effect and man-made noise. Even though the experiments attempted to maintain a steady and unchanging environment, it was unsuccessful in finding out the regularity of RSSI signal. The RSSI signals variance and its strength are not directly related to each other, but they are individually depended on the environment complexity.

In [2], a unique unbiased estimator was proposed to estimate the location of a signal source using relative position of sensors in indoor unit. The Received signal strength (RSS), time of arrival (TOA) and time difference of arrival (TDOA) are used for source localization. Generally the estimators are biased whose MSE and MLE grow exponentially with the noise power. But This estimator uses MMSE for which both magnitude of the bias and the MSE are bounded in the noise power.

In fact, WLAN-based location estimation takes the RSSI and applies either statistical approach or deterministic approach to identify the location of the object inside the indoor unit. The statistical approach which uses Maximum Likelihood (ML), MMSE etc performs poorer because in indoor environments, near/far effect, multipath fading and shadowing gives large variations in RSSI measurements. [3]

In [4], a hybrid RSS-RTT localization scheme was proposed and simulated in an indoor environment. It outperforms the conventional RSS-based estimator and RTT-based estimator for localization. WIFI RTT/RSS/PDR/Map fusion system was proposed to improve the performance of smart phone based indoor positioning system in terms of particle improvement, propagation, and weight update [5]. In [6], a method that combines calibrated RTT and processed received signal strength is used to improve the performance of the indoor positioning system. [7] combines Wi-Fi RTT and RSS within a conformal prediction framework to produce accurate position estimates with uncertainty bounds. The hybrid RTT-RSS method outperforms single-signal approaches across multiple real environments. Therefore, in this paper we attempt to model RTT estimation using the RSS.

III. Proposed System

This section describes how RTT and RSS data are collected and how the proposed model is identified and validated.

III.1. Data Collection

We consider an infrastructure-based wireless network for this experiment, in which an access point and multiple wireless nodes are considered. Five different places inside the WIFI covered area is identified and the RSS and RTT readings from access point are measured with fixed time interval in order to apply time series analysis. The Table 1 shows summary of the RSS and RTT value collected for this experiment.

III.2. Data Analysis

In statistics, the autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation are used to characterize temporal dependence in time series data. They quantify the extent to which current readings are linearly related to history values. Therefore, in this paper, we attempt to model the RTT-RTT using time series analysis. The autocorrelation measures the linear independence between a time series

and its lagged version. For a time, series $\{Y_t\}$ with mean μ and variance σ^2 , the autocorrelation at lag k is defined as

$$\rho_k = \frac{\gamma_k}{\gamma_0} = \frac{\text{Cov}(Y_t, Y_{t-k})}{\text{Var}(Y_t)}$$

The partial autocorrelation function at lag represents the correlation between Y_t and Y_{t-k} that is not accounted for by lags 1 through k-1. It is defined as

$$\alpha_k = \text{Corr}(Y_t - \hat{Y}_t^{(k-1)}, Y_{t-k} - \hat{Y}_{t-k}^{(k-1)})$$

TABLE I. RTT Data used for Model Identification

Loc	Dist from AP in Meter	Min RTT (ms)	Max RTT (ms)	Mean RTT (ms)	Var (ms)
1	2.15	1	89.3	18.276	464.455
5	4.77	1.1	109.8	17.384	458.113
3	6.45	1.	121.5	19.413	518.609
2	7.03	1.5	147.6	22.136	508.453
4	10.58	1.1	95.1	16.240	416.638
1	2.15	1.2	148.1	17.885	591.373
5	4.77	1.1	102.5	19.114	381.372
3	6.45	1.2	84.7	19.865	372.734
2	7.03	1.4	92.7	22.985	507.981
4	10.58	1.4	107.8	20.376	576.565
1	2.15	1	104.8	16.399	459.061
5	4.77	1.1	93.6	17.845	626.625
3	6.45	1.2	94.3	15.280	404.206
2	7.03	1.3	86	17.065	456.672
4	10.58	1.1	91.9	14.399	409.906

TABLE 2. RSS Data used for Model Identification

Loc	Dist from AP in Meter	Min RTT (ms)	Max RTT (ms)	Mean RTT (ms)	Var (ms)
1	2.15	-80.130	-51.650	-70.634	32.478
5	4.77	-78.750	-41.780	-66.641	36.825
3	6.45	-80.780	-51.00	-68.451	33.682
2	7.03	-80.400	-29.620	-70.892	70.459
4	10.58	-77.00	-39.400	-68.188	47.542
1	2.15	-83.780	-55.400	-73.433	34.923
5	4.77	-77.450	-45.500	-66.980	24.043
3	6.45	-82.780	-48.780	-71.355	36.860
2	7.03	-86.720	-59.750	-79.941	25.496
4	10.58	-81.00	-46.670	-65.260	30.004
1	2.15	-68.390	-25.070	-61.104	43.231
5	4.77	-60.00	-41.800	-53.765	10.135
3	6.45	-64.670	-34.940	-58.252	19.652
2	7.03	-65.670	-30.920	-59.867	38.175
4	10.58	-62.130	-20.440	-49.016	129.441

III.3. Model Identification

To identify the appropriate model for RTT-RSS, first we applied first order differencing over the data in order to remove the seasonal components in the time series. The autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation are applied over the time series and it is found at lag 3 of autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation are significant. Based on the auto correlation and partial autocorrelation, we found VARIMA model is suitable for RTT prediction using multivariant approach with order (3,1,3) where 3 indicates AR order and 1 indicates first order differencing and 3 indicates MA order

III.4. RTT Estimation using VARIMA(3,1,3) Model

The proposed model predicts the future RTT value using the previous RTT and RSS value with 95% of accuracy.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{RTT}(t) = & 0.2022 \text{ RTT}(t-1) + 0.4871 \text{ RTT}(t-2) - 0.3108 \\ & \text{RTT}(t-3) - 0.1033 \text{ RSS}(t-1) + 0.034 \text{ RSS}(t-2) - 0.3108 \\ & \text{RTT}(t-3) - 0.2931. \end{aligned}$$

III.5. Model Validation

The positive coefficients of RTT indicate the persistence in delay behavior and the negative coefficient of RTT suggest damping of long-term delay effects. The negative coefficients of RSS imply that improved signal strength leads to reduced RTT and the constant term accounts for baseline network delay. Residuals are analyzed to verify model adequacy and found hold good. The multivariant Ljung-Box test confirmed whiteness and the estimated parameters are statistically significant at the 95% confidence level

IV. CONCLUSION

The results demonstrate that incorporating RSS into RTT prediction improves modeling accuracy. The VARIMA(3,1,3) model effectively captures both temporal dynamics and cross-dependence between physical-layer and network-layer metrics. This paper presented a bivariate VARIMA-based approach for RTT prediction using RSS measurements collected at equal intervals. After systematic data analysis and model identification, a VARIMA(3,1,3) model was developed and validated. Experimental results confirm that RSS significantly enhances RTT prediction accuracy, making the proposed model suitable for wireless performance monitoring and adaptive network control.

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